

INTELLECTUALISM AND ANALYTICAL THINKING: ARE THEY RELATED?

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ABSTRACT

Analytical thinking is a vital part of intellectualism, although their relationship has not been directly examined. Therefore, in a representative Slovak sample ($N = 410$), we examined a newly developed Intellectualism-Anti-Intellectualism Scale (IAIS) by Marques et al. (2017) and its relationships to two indicators of analytical thinking - cognitive biases and cognitive reflection. Moreover, we focused on the three analytical thinking prerequisites - cognitive ability, numerical mindware, and dispositions to analytical thinking. Our results favor the positive correlation between analytical thinking - i.e., lower bias susceptibility and higher cognitive reflection - and intellectualism. While cognitive ability showed no significant association, subjective measures of analytic thinking and numeracy were the strongest correlates of intellectualism. These results indicated that intellectualism taps mostly (but not only) into the motivation and/or predisposition to think analytically. Finally, education appeared, consistently with previous research, as a significant predictor of intellectualism, which opened up new avenues for further research practical implications.

Keywords: intellectualism; analytical thinking; Intellectualism-Anti-Intellectualism Scale; cognitive biases; thinking dispositions; education

1. INTRODUCTION

Intellectualism is a capacity to ponder in detail about things, ideally without the influence of emotions (Hofstadter, 1963). It also refers to practicing and developing abilities such as problem-solving or critical thinking. Thus, intellectualism appeals as a noble act that should be cultivated. However, doubts about intellectual activities empowered anti-intellectual movements, which contemned of critical thinking and open-mindedness (Hofstadter, 1963; Žuk & Žuk, 2020). Moreover, anti-intellectualism has played a negative role in the recent coronavirus pandemic while being associated with lower compliance with social distancing measures and higher susceptibility to misperceptions about COVID-19 (Merkley & Loewen, 2021). Such behavior might also point at problems with analytical thinking, which is considered a cornerstone of intellectualism. Yet, their mutual relationships have not been directly examined. Thus, our current study examines the relationships between intellectualism and several aspects of analytical thinking: cognitive ability, analytical thinking dispositions, numerical processing, and susceptibility to cognitive biases.

1.1 Measuring Intellectualism vs. Anti-intellectualism

While (anti-)intellectualism has become an attractive construct for examination in social sciences (e.g., Marques et al., 2017; Merkley & Loewen, 2021; Žuk & Žuk, 2020), measurements scales are lacking. Inspired by Hofstadter's (1963) and Rigney's work (1991) on anti-intellectualism, Eigenberger and Sealander (2001) created the Student Anti-intellectualism Scale (SAIS). The scale tapped unreflective instrumentalism – a type of anti-intellectualism that reflects a preference for materialistic gains over higher education (Rigney, 1991). Anti-intellectualism measured by SAIS showed positive correlations with dogmatism and authoritarianism and negative associations with openness to experience, learning style, and

critical thinking. However, using the scale in the general population was problematic because it primarily focused on university students.

The limited use of the SAIS (Eigenberger & Sealander, 2001) led Marques et al. (2017) to develop a new Intellectualism-Anti-Intellectualism Scale (IAIS) to capture intellection – an affective state perceived while engaged in intellectual activities. The intellectualism measured by IAIS exhibited a positive relationship with cognitive flexibility, reflecting the ability to adjust thinking styles to different situations and a strong positive correlation with the Need for cognition. Notably, the IAIS and the Need for cognition shared similar relationships with epistemic preference and dogmatism. Yet, in comparison with the Need for cognition, IAIS was less strongly related to the Need for cognitive closure and personal need for structure. One of the explanations might be that with an intellectual and analytical setup, one does not need to come to specific knowledge, but with the Need for cognition, getting specific knowledge is the goal. Consequently, Marques et al. (2017) suggest intellection and the Need for cognition are strongly related albeit distinct concepts. Finally, age in student subsamples and education displayed positive correlations with the IAIS, indicating that experience gained through aging and the university environment is positively associated with scores in the IAIS.

1.2 Intellectualism and Analytical Thinking

While analytical thinking is considered a complement of intellectualism, their mutual association has not been adequately examined. Marques et al. (2017) examined correlations between IAIS and several concepts relevant to analytical thinking, such as analytical thinking disposition (Need for cognition) and intelligence; however, we believe it is vital to scrutinize other relationships as well. Therefore, we extended the examination by two indicators of analytical thinking - cognitive reflection and susceptibility to cognitive biases (Pennycook et al., 2015; Stanovich et al., 2016).

Cognitive biases are in modern dual-process theories (e.g., Evans & Stanovich, 2013) related to intuitive (Type 1) thinking. This type is autonomous, controlless, and linked to various mental shortcuts called heuristics. Although intuitive heuristics may be helpful in many situations, they may also lead us astray. In such situations, we need to apply deliberate, consciously controlled, but demanding analytical (Type 2) thinking. Analytical thinking enables capacities such as hypothetical thinking and suppressing potentially wrong intuitive responses. Importantly, Type 2 thinking is also associated with intellectualism (Marques et al., 2017). Since analytical thinking is related to lower susceptibility to cognitive biases, we expect that intellectualism will be associated with lower susceptibility to cognitive biases. However, cognitive reflection represented by suppressing potentially incorrect intuitive responses should associate positively with intellectualism.

Furthermore, according to Stanovich et al. (2011, 2016), analytical thinking relies on three prerequisites – cognitive ability (i.e., intelligence), specific knowledge (i.e., mindware), and an analytical thinking disposition. First, Marques et al. (2017) found no correlation between intellectualism and abstract intelligence, but their subsample was very small. Therefore, we included intelligence measurement among a larger and culturally different sample. Second, specific knowledge (mindware) is usually probabilistic or numerical competence that is necessary to understand the nature of the task and calculate the correct response (Klaczynski, 2014; Stanovich et al., 2011, 2016). Then, thanks to this mindware, favoring analytical and usually normatively correct responses over intuitive responses is more probable. We included subjective and objective numerical ability measures commonly used for assessing mindware (e.g., Klaczynski et al., 2014). We hypothesized that when specific knowledge contributes to analytical thinking, it should correlate positively with intellectualism. The third complement of analytical thinking - an analytical thinking disposition (e.g., Need for cognition; Stanovich et al., 2016) – appears to positively correlate with intellectualism (Marques et al., 2017). Hence,

our final aim is to verify these findings and extend them with new concepts of Actively open-minded thinking and Faith in intuition (Epstein et al., 1996). We expect intellectualism to share positive associations with the Need for cognition and Actively open-minded thinking, but a negative correlation with the disposition to think intuitively (Faith in intuition).

To sum up, the current study examines the relationships between intellectualism, analytical thinking, and susceptibility to cognitive biases that not only relate to analytical but also critical thinking (West et al., 2008). Importantly, while Marques et al. (2017) focused almost solely on subjective measures tapping preference of and motivation for various thinking styles, our study brings an important extension by including also objective measures of analytical thinking, numerical competence, and cognitive ability. This will allow us to compare the relationships between the intellectualism and several key constructs related to analytic thinking both at the level of subjective evaluation and objective performance. Based on previous arguments, we expect positive associations between intellectualism and analytical thinking. Finally, given the relative novelty of the Intellectualism-Anti-Intellectualism scale (Marques et al., 2017), we also conducted a confirmatory factor analysis and examined the associations between IAIS and demographic characteristics of our participants to complement previous analyses on the basic psychometric information and criterion validity of the scale.

2. METHOD

2.1 Participants

We collected data via an online survey distributed through a recruitment agency. The sample consisted of 410 people (Slovaks, 207 female, 203 male) aged between 18 and 86 years ($M = 43.26$, $SD = 15.29$) and was representative of the gender and age distribution of the general population. Most participants reported finishing high school with a diploma (42.9%) or having at least some college degree (46.5%). A small proportion of the sample attained elementary

education or high school without a diploma (10.5%). The collected data were a part of a larger study that aimed at identifying individual difference predictors of susceptibility to metacognitive biases.

2.2 Materials

Before all analyses, every self-report measure below was subjected to a minimum residual exploratory factor analysis (EFA) with oblimin rotation to determine its dimensionality. For every measure, the scree plot indicated one dominant factor (single factor with eigenvalue > 1), and all items loaded substantially on this single factor (all factor loadings $> .30$). The only exception was the Actively open-minded thinking scale (AOT). While EFA showed a single factor, loadings of 4 items of this measure were below $.30$, and the overall reliability of the scale was low. Therefore, for all further analyses, we decided to exclude items with low loadings to increase the internal consistency of the AOT scale.

2.2.1 Intellectualism-Anti-Intellectualism Scale

Intellectualism-Anti-Intellectualism scale (IAIS) by Marques et al. (2017) taps the degree to which one enjoys and prefers intellectual activities. The scale consists of ten statements (e.g., “*I deliberately seek out sources of intellectual stimulation*”). Participants rated their agreement with every statement using a scale from 1 (“*completely disagree*”) to 5 (“*completely agree*”). Half of the items are reverse scored. Average rating on the ten items represents participants’ overall intellectualism score ($M = 2.92$, $SD = 0.70$, $\alpha = .82$), with higher scores indicating higher intellectualism. The wording of all scale items with their respective descriptive statistics is presented in Table A1 in Appendix A.

2.2.2 Analytical thinking tasks

Susceptibility to cognitive biases comprised 36 items selected from previous research (Šrol, 2019). Specifically, tasks measured belief bias, base-rate neglect, conjunction fallacy, ratio bias, gambler's fallacy and framing effect (example items can be found in Stanovich et al., 2016). Before every task, participants read instructions to familiarize themselves with the problems. The average z-score from the heuristic answers on 36 items was used as a measure of bias susceptibility ($\alpha = .82$).

Cognitive reflection was measured by ten items that evoked compelling but wrong intuitive responses. Three items are from the original Frederick's (2005) test but with changed content and numbers, complemented with seven additional similar problems (e.g., "If it takes 3 printers 3 minutes to print 3 newspapers, how long would it take 100 printers to print 100 newspapers?"). Sum of correct answers was used as a measure of cognitive reflection ($M = 5.52$, $SD = 2.54$, $\alpha = .77$).

2.2.3 Numeracy measures

Berlin numeracy test is an objective measure of participants' ability to work with numerical and probabilistic information (Cokely et al., 2012). We employed the open-ended response format (for the full wording of the items, see appendix in Cokely et al., 2012). The sum of correctly answered items was used as an indicator of participants' numeracy ($M = 1.13$, $SD = 1.04$, $\alpha = .45$).

Subjective numeracy scale (SNS) was an additional self-report numeracy measure (Fagerlin et al., 2007). The scale consisted of eight questions relating to the ability to use numerical information (e.g., "How good are you at working with fractions?") and the preference for numerical over other formats of information (e.g., "How often do you find numerical information to be useful?"). Responses to the items were on a 6-point scale. The subjective

numeracy of participants was measured as an average rating on the eight items ($M = 4.97$, $SD = 1.08$, $\alpha = .85$).

2.2.4 Cognitive ability

Cognitive ability was measured by the Vienna matrix test (Klose et al., 2002), which is a standardized measure of the general cognitive ability resembling the Raven's progressive matrices. The test consists of 24 items of increasing difficulty in which participants need to find a pattern in a complex 3 x 3 picture matrix and choose one of the eight options to complete the test under a 24-minute limit. The sum of correctly answered problems was used as an indicator of participants' cognitive ability ($M = 13.49$, $SD = 5.17$, $\alpha = .86$).

2.2.5 Thinking disposition scales

We asked participants to rate their agreement with the thinking disposition items on a scale from 1 ("*completely disagree*") to 5 ("*completely agree*"). An indicator of the respective thinking disposition was an average rating for every scale.

Actively open-minded thinking scale (AOT) consisted of eight items (e.g., "*People should take into consideration evidence that goes against their beliefs*") that measured the tendency toward considering opposing evidence and avoiding dogmatism when making up one's mind about some issue (Baron et al., 2015). Higher scores indicate a higher inclination to actively open-minded thinking. As mentioned, four items were excluded based on EFA to increase the reliability of the scale. The average rating on the remaining four items was 3.55 ($SD = 0.72$, $\alpha = .59$).

Rational-experiential inventory consisted of a five-item *Need for cognition* (NFC; e.g., "*I prefer complex to simple problems*"), and five-item *Faith in Intuition* (FI; e.g., "*I believe in trusting my hunches*") scales taken from Study 2 of Epstein et al. (1996). Epstein et al. report high

correlations between both five-item versions and their original longer counterparts ($r = .90$ for NFC; $r = .85$ for FI), which are used as the standard thinking dispositions measures in studies on cognitive biases (e.g., Dewberry et al., 2013; Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015). We calculated average rating on the five items of Need for cognition ($M = 3.44$, $SD = 0.74$, $\alpha = .67$) and Faith in Intuition ($M = 3.67$, $SD = 0.73$, $\alpha = .81$) scales.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Confirmatory factor analysis of IAIS

First, to confirm the original one-factor structure of the IAIS, we performed a confirmatory factor analysis with DWLS estimation carried out with the *lavaan* package (Rosseel, 2012) of the R software. All items were allowed to load onto a single factor. The one-factor model fitted data well, $\chi^2(35) = 93.65$, $p < .001$, CFI = .97, TLI = .96, RMSEA = .064, confirming the original structure reported by the authors of the scale (Marques et al., 2017). Table A1 (Appendix A) provides standardized factor loadings for the individual items. All loadings were significant and above .38. Then, we calculated mean intellectualism scores for all participants by averaging their rating on the items of IAIS. The average intellectualism score was used in the analyses below to determine differences in intellectualism based on gender, age, and education. Age and gender differences in all other variables reported in this study are in Appendix B.

3.2 The relationships between intellectualism and analytical thinking indicators

In Table 1, we present the correlations between intellectualism and all analytical thinking indicators. First, intellectualism had moderate to strong correlations with analytical thinking dispositions - open-minded thinking and the Need for cognition. Peculiarly, Faith in intuition was not negatively related to intellectualism.

Considering numeracy measures, IAIS exhibited moderate positive associations with subjective evaluation and objective competence in working with numerical information. The association was a bit stronger in the case of subjective numeracy; however, the difference in the two dependent correlations was not statistically significant, $Z = 1.76, p = .078$. Interestingly, while intellectualism was moderately associated with objective numeracy, there was no significant correlation with cognitive ability.

Table 1. Correlations between intellectualism and various indicators of analytic thinking

	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
1. Intellectualism	1							
2. Actively open-minded thinking	.16	1						
3. Need for cognition	.49	.24	1					
4. Faith in intuition	.02	-.27	.09	1				
5. Subjective numeracy	.32	.23	.32	-.04	1			
6. Objective numeracy	.23	.27	.27	-.04	.41	1		
7. Cognitive ability	.09	.20	.12	-.14	.37	.46	1	
8. Cognitive reflection	.18	.32	.21	-.15	.46	.54	.53	1
9. Bias susceptibility	-.21	-.29	-.18	.17	-.37	-.52	-.44	-.52

Note. The correlations are based on 410 observations. Correlation coefficients of $r > .10$ are significant at $p < .05$, $r > .13$ are significant at $p < .01$, and $r > .17$ are significant at $p < .001$. Significant correlation coefficients ($p < .05$) are in bold.

While intellectualism showed more or less expected relationships with various prerequisites for analytical thinking (thinking dispositions, numeracy, cognitive ability), we also examined its correlation with two direct indicators of analytical thinking - cognitive reflection and lower susceptibility to cognitive biases. As expected, cognitive reflection positively and bias susceptibility negatively correlated with intellectualism. Both correlations were, however, relatively modest and similar in strength to the correlations between the thinking dispositions variables and direct analytical thinking indicators.

3.3. Differences in IAIS based on age, gender, and education

While Marques et al. (2017) reported a significant correlation between IAIS and age in some of their student subsamples, they did not find the correlation with age among community and convenience subsamples with a wider age distribution. Consistently with their findings, we have observed no correlation between IAIS scores and age in our sample, which spanned a wide age, $r(410) = .034, p = .49$. For a direct comparison with the results of Marques et al. (2017), who showed the difference in IAIS between people with and without tertiary education, we provide the comparison in intellectualism between participants with tertiary education ($M = 3.09, SD = 0.75$) and without tertiary (university) education ($M = 2.77, SD = 0.62$), $t(408) = -4.68, p < .001$, $M_{diff} = -0.317, 95\% CI [-0.45, -0.18]$, $d = 0.46$. Although the difference in our study ($d = 0.46$) was smaller than the one ($d = 0.70$) reported by Marques et al. (2017), in general, we observed the same trend - people with higher education exhibited higher intellectualism.

Also, consistently with Marques et al. (2017), we found no significant difference between men ($M = 2.95, SD = 0.70$) and women ($M = 2.89, SD = 0.71$) in their IAIS scores, $t(408) = 0.92, p = .36, M_{diff} = 0.06, 95\% CI [-0.07, 0.20]$, $d = 0.09$. Men scored a little higher on the IAIS scale in our sample than women, but the difference was of negligible effect size and was not statistically significant. Therefore, gender does not seem to affect the enjoyment and preference for intellectual activities.

3.4 Predicting intellectualism scores with demographic factors and analytical thinking indicators

In the final step, we extended our examination of the predictors of intellectualism by conducting a hierarchical linear regression analysis with demographic factors (entered in step 1) and analytical thinking indicators (entered in step 2) as independent predictors of the scores on IAIS. We present the results of the analysis in Table 2. As can be seen from the upper part of the table, and consistently with analyses presented above, the demographic factors explained

relatively little variance (around 5%) in intellectualism. The only factor which significantly predicted IAIS scores at the first step of the regression was education.

Table 2. Linear regression analysis predicting intellectualism scores

Predictor	<i>b</i>	SE	β	95% CI	<i>p</i>
<i>Step 1</i>					
<i>F</i> (3, 406) = 7.87, <i>p</i> < .001, adj. <i>R</i> ² = 0.048					
Age	0.00	0.002	.06	[-.03, .15]	.202
Gender	0.01	0.062	.01	[-.08, .09]	.889
Tertiary education	0.18	0.064	.13	 [.04, .22]	.006
<i>Step 2</i>					
<i>Model comparison: F</i> (8, 398) = 17.3, <i>p</i> < .001, ΔR^2 = 0.244					
Actively open-minded thinking	-0.02	0.046	-.02	[-.11, .08]	.700
Need for cognition	0.40	0.044	.42	 [.33, .51]	< .001
Faith in intuition	-0.01	0.044	-.00	[-.09, .09]	.980
Objective numeracy	0.03	0.038	.05	[-.06, .16]	.397
Subjective numeracy	0.09	0.034	.13	 [.03, .24]	.009
Bias susceptibility	-0.20	0.104	-.10	[-.21, .00]	.057
Cognitive ability	-0.01	0.008	-.06	[-.18, .05]	.266
Cognitive reflection	-0.01	0.016	-.03	[-.15, .08]	.585
<i>Full model</i>					
<i>F</i> (11, 398) = 15.41, <i>p</i> < .001, adj. <i>R</i> ² = 0.279					

Note. For every predictor, we show unstandardized coefficients (*b*), their standard error (*SE*), standardized coefficients (β) with their 95% confidence interval, and statistical significance at the final step of the regression. Next, the table contains adjusted *R*² for the first step and the final step, together with its change between the first and second models. Significant regression coefficients (*p* < .05) are in bold. Education was coded as 0 = “less than tertiary education”, 1 = “tertiary education”.

Inclusion of the analytic thinking indicators led to a 24% increase in explained variance in intellectualism that is over and above the variance accounted for by the demographic factors in the first step of the regression. Although most of these predictors were associated with intellectualism (see Table 1), only two variables - Need for cognition and subjective numeracy - significantly and independently predicted IAIS scores after accounting for other predictors. This accords with the previous correlational analysis, as the two variables exhibited the

strongest correlations with intellectualism. Finally, to obtain the most succinct model predicting intellectualism, we supplemented this analysis with a backward stepwise regression (for results, see Appendix C). The results were completely consistent with those presented in the main manuscript, with one exception. Bias susceptibility, which did not significantly predict intellectualism in the analysis described above ($\beta = -.10, p = .057$), emerged as a significant predictor in the model selected by the backward stepwise regression ($\beta = -.10, p = .045$) along with education, Need for cognition, and subjective numeracy.

4. DISCUSSION

Intellectualism represents a behavior in which one seeks and enjoys deep pondering and in which analytical thinking takes a substantial part. Previous studies measuring intellectualism/anti-intellectualism indicated associations with some aspects of analytical thinking, but these were rather indirect (Eigenberger & Sealander, 2001; Marques et al., 2017). Therefore, we focused on this relationship directly and more extensively by employing the IAIS scale, cognitive reflection, and a series of heuristics and biases tasks, as well as three prerequisites of analytical thinking - cognitive ability, mindware, and dispositions to analytical thinking.

Generally, our results indicate that analytical thinking is positively associated with intellectualism. In line with our hypotheses, cognitive bias susceptibility was negatively, and cognitive reflection was positively correlated with intellectualism. Observed relationships represent strong evidence suggesting that intellectualism is directly associated with analytical thinking and the ability to recognize and suppress incorrect intuitive responses. Also, objective numeracy, as an important mindware prerequisite of analytical thinking, was positively related to intellectualism. And yet, similarly to Marques et al. (2017), we found no correlation between

intellectualism and cognitive ability. This might be because although general intelligence is one of the prerequisites of the ability to think analytically and suppress the intuitive responses to various heuristic and biases tasks, it is still quite distinct from analytical thinking (Stanovich et al., 2016). Be that as it may, the correlations with the objective measures of numeric competence and analytic thinking indicate that intellectualism does not reflect purely the attitudinal or motivational aspect of thinking, as suggested by Marques et al. (2017). At least to some degree, people scoring high on intellectualism are better predisposed to engage in analytical thinking and are better at solving numerical problems than those with lower intellectualism.

While there were significant associations between intellectualism and several objective measures of analytic thinking, it was obvious from the regression results that intellectualism shares stronger associations with subjective measures of analytic and numerical thinking. Especially, the substantial correlation between intellectualism and the Need for cognition indicates that IAIS taps predominantly into the motivation and/or predisposition to think analytically (see Marques et al., 2017). The relationships between intellectualism, subjective numeracy competence and other analytical thinking dispositions also mostly accorded with our predictions and previous studies. Thus, subjective numeracy and Actively open-minded thinking were positively related to intellectualism. Nevertheless, since the reliability of the Actively open-minded thinking scale was low, some caution should be applied when interpreting these results. And yet, Faith in intuition showed no substantial correlation with intellectualism. As argued by Epstein et al. (1996), this difference may be because the tendencies toward intuitive and analytical thought represent two separate constructs rather than opposing ends of a single continuum. Similarly, the preference and enjoyment of intellectual activities do not seem to indicate absolute avoidance of intuitive thought.

Finally, as the IAIS instrument for measuring intellectualism is relatively novel, we conducted several additional analyses to examine its psychometric properties. The confirmatory factor

analysis of the IAIS scale showed a good fit with a one-factor model, which accords with Marques et al. (2017). Moreover, we found that education significantly predicted intellectualism. Higher IAIS scores among tertiary-educated people compared to people without tertiary education were also found by Marques et al. (2017). The authors argued that university education fosters intellectualism by providing an environment where people are encouraged to display intellectual curiosity. Gender and age of participants were not associated with intellectualism, and this is again in line with the findings of Marques et al. (2017).

4.1 Conclusion

As Hofstadter (1963) remarked, anti-intellectualism has inauspicious effects on various aspects of modern society. Recently, the evident and arguably dangerous aspect in which anti-intellectualism acted was the COVID-19 pandemic. For example, Merkley and Loewen (2021) observed that higher anti-intellectualism led to a higher tendency to ignore specific COVID-19 measures. The results of Žuk & Žuk (2020) indicated that anti-intellectualism, together with populism, might relate to lower vaccination rates. Moreover, Merkley (2020) observed that anti-intellectualism substantially predicted opposing opinions against scientifically justified consensus, which also includes the relevance of vaccination. Importantly, his results suggest that higher anti-intellectualism affected by populist rhetoric even increased the mistrust in the scientific consensus. Eventually, these findings should be a warning and a call for politicians to be more responsible in order to protect society. Yet, a way to decrease anti-intellectualism in society stems from the findings of Marques et al. (2017) and ours. It lies in proper education, which promotes creative, analytical, and critical thinking.

Ethics Approval

Ethical review and approval were not required for the study on human participants in accordance with the local legislation and institutional requirements. All participants were informed about the terms, conditions, and procedures of the study in the Informed Consent at the beginning of the survey.

Conflict of Interests

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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APPENDIX A

Table A1. Item and scale-level analysis of the Intellectualism-Anti-Intellectualism Scale

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>α if deleted</i>	<i>λ</i>
1. Working on difficult intellectual problems is enjoyable and stimulating for me	3.44	1.09	.81	.57
2. I generally find physical or recreational activities more satisfying than intellectual activities (R)	2.68	1.06	.82	.38
3. I tend to feel somewhat bored and impatient when dealing with remote, theoretical problems (R)	2.89	1.10	.81	.53
4. Intellectual discovery is ok, but I prefer other forms of excitement (R)	2.72	1.04	.80	.63
5. I'm probably the sort of person who would find it thrilling to be engrossed in a research project	3.08	1.26	.80	.70
6. I deliberately seek out sources of intellectual stimulation	3.01	1.16	.79	.73
7. I have more exciting things to do than sit around and think all day long (R)	2.64	1.15	.81	.50
8. I feel compelled to work on conceptual problems, even when I don't have to	2.70	1.05	.81	.53
9. One of my favorite activities is discovering alternative ways of explaining a particular phenomenon	2.92	1.22	.81	.57
10. The process of examining a concept in great detail is generally unappealing to me (R)	3.09	1.14	.81	.52

Note. The table shows mean ratings on individual items of the IAIS with their respective standard deviations. It also shows Cronbach's alpha reliability estimate for the scale after the respective item is deleted and standardized factor loadings (λ) taken from the confirmatory factor analysis. All loadings are significant at $p < .001$.

APPENDIX B

Table B1. Age and gender differences in all measures reported in the present study

	Men (<i>n</i> = 203)	Women (<i>n</i> = 207)	difference test	age correlation
Actively open-minded thinking	3.58 (0.75)	3.51 (0.75)	$t = 1.00, d = 0.10$	-.04
Need for Cognition	3.46 (0.75)	3.42 (0.73)	$t = 0.49, d = 0.05$	-.00
Faith in Intuition	3.56 (0.74)	3.77 (0.71)	$t = -2.98, d = 0.29^{**}$.03
Subjective numeracy	4.16 (1.08)	3.78 (1.04)	$t = 3.60, d = 0.36^{***}$	-.07
Objective numeracy	1.26 (1.09)	1.00 (0.96)	$t = 3.08, d = 0.30^{**}$	-.20 ^{***}
Cognitive ability	13.4 (5.09)	13.6 (5.25)	$t = 2.61, d = 0.26^{**}$	-.38 ^{***}
Cognitive reflection	5.91 (2.58)	5.14 (2.46)	$t = -0.36, d = 0.04$	-.08
Bias susceptibility	0.05 (0.40)	-0.05 (0.34)	$t = 2.47, d = 0.24^*$	-.27 ^{***}

Note. The table shows means and standard deviations of scores for all measures separately for male and female participants, and the results of an independent t-test to compare these values (Cohen's *d* as a measure of effect size). The last column shows the Pearson's correlations between scores on every measure and age in the whole sample. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$.

APPENDIX C

Table C1. Backward stepwise linear regression analysis predicting intellectualism scores

Predictor	<i>b</i>	SE	β	95% CI	<i>p</i>
Tertiary education	0.18	0.063	.13	 [.04, .21]	.005
Need for cognition	0.40	0.042	.42	 [.34, .51]	< .001
Subjective numeracy	0.09	0.032	.14	 [.04, .24]	.005
Bias susceptibility	-0.18	0.092	-.10	 [-.19, .00]	.045
Cognitive ability	-0.01	0.007	-.08	[-.18, .01]	.087
<i>Full model</i>	<i>F</i> (5, 404) = 33.7, <i>p</i> < .001, adj. <i>R</i> ² = 0.286				

Note. For every predictor, we show unstandardized coefficients (*b*), their standard error (*SE*), standardized coefficients (β) with their 95% confidence interval, and statistical significance at the final step of the backward stepwise regression. Next, the table contains adjusted *R*² for the final model. Significant regression coefficients (*p* < .05) are in bold. Education was coded as 0 = “less than tertiary education”, 1 = “tertiary education”.